

Manager's Management Style, Employees' Satisfaction and Employees' Productivity at North Park Noodle House

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ABSTRACT

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This research study aimed to examine the manager's management style, including the parameters such as the autocratic, consultative, democratic, and *laisse - faire*, at North Park Noodle House. Additionally, it explored the relationship between manager's management style, and employees' satisfaction and productivity. The study sought to determine whether there were significant relationships between the manager's management style and the level of employees' satisfaction, as well as between the manager's management style and employees' productivity. Furthermore, it examined the connection between employees' satisfaction and employees' productivity. This study employed a descriptive-correlational research design, focusing on the manager's management style, employees' satisfaction, and employees' productivity as the key variables. The findings revealed a significant relationship between the manager's management style in terms of democratic, and *laisse- faire* and the level of employees' satisfaction, while parameters such as autocratic and consultative showed that there were no significant relationship with employees' satisfaction. Additionally, the results showed that the level of productivity was only influenced by the manager's management style in terms of *laisse – faire* and the three other factors were not significant. Lastly, the study confirmed that employees' productivity is also dependent on employee satisfaction, highlighting that higher satisfaction resulted to increased productivity.

KEYWORDS:

Manager's management style, employees' satisfaction, employees' productivity, casual dining restaurants.

INTRODUCTION

"If you spend too much time thinking about a thing, you shall never get it done", "If you want to build high performance organization, you have got to play chess, not checkers" and "It does not matter whether you do small or big job; what matters is job contentment". All these recognizable quotable lines by Bruce Lee and Mark Miller are tantamount to management style, employees' productivity and employees' satisfaction. These three mentioned subject matters played a major role throughout this research study and researcher strongly believe that these were indeed very important to address as they can contribute to the growth and profitability of the company.

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In any organization, the manager is set to perform multiple roles and how they handle various situations will depend on their style of management. According to Bucata (2016), management styles reflect the way managers are exercising their functions, the role they have in work management and organization, training and stimulating subordinates to meet objectives. Meanwhile, employee productivity, also called workplace productivity, is an assessment of an employees' or a group of employees' efficiencies. It is evaluated by looking at the total workforce or employee output in a given time. In most cases, the productivity of an individual will be assessed in comparison to the average output of other employees doing similar work (Harness, 2018). On the other hand, Johnson (2020), defined employee satisfaction as the level of happiness workers experience. Employee satisfaction is an important element within business because it directly relates to the productivity of employees. These three are interrelated. They are involved in the success of a company and this is the main focus of the study.

Based on the study of Okon (2016). Result also showed that participative management style was more positively related with employees' performance than other management styles. Hence, there is a need for operators of small scale business enterprises to involve their employees in decision making so as to improve their performance.

According to Harley (2016) stated that in a company, employee satisfaction is supremely essential because it is what depends on efficiency. If your workers are happy, in optimal time they will deliver superior quality production and contribute to increasing profits. Satisfied employees are also more likely to be innovative and creative and come up with breakthroughs that allow a business to grow and change positively with time and changing market circumstances.

Gupta and Parmar (2018) found that goals and objectives setting, performance rewards given to employees and performance appraisal feedback all three independent variables of performance appraisal influenced employee productivity that is taken as a dependent variable. Study found that set goal motivate employees to achieve target, rewards given to employees for their positive result and feedback help to identify the strength and weaknesses of employee.

In doing this research, there are many things that need to be considered. Considerations may differ depending on the field of business and/or field of work. That is the reason why this study chose a particular field which is the field of hospitality industry. The said industry includes restaurant, hotels, theme parks, travel agencies, transportation, and events planning. Still, all may seem broad, that is the reason why the proponent of this study chose a specific field and that is Casual Dining Restaurant.

Casual-dining restaurants offer food similar to fast-casual establishments but with a table-service dining atmosphere. Most casual-dining restaurants provide a family-friendly environment. The menus at casual dining restaurants are usually more extensive than at fast-casual places. Casual-dining restaurants employ waiters who take customers' orders and serve the food. The prices of casual-dining restaurants are lower than at fine-dining restaurants, but a little more expensive than at fast-casual places. These restaurants may serve a variety of pastas, chicken dishes and simple seafood dishes. Some have highly specialized menus, but others serve a broad range of cuisine (Johnson, 2020). The specific target restaurant of this study is the NorthPark Noodles House.

The said restaurant is known in delivering real and freshly cooked food at generous servings and reasonable prices. According to their company website, North Park is a homegrown business owned and founded by Rafael Soon of the North Park Group of Restaurants. The first North Park establishment opened in T. Pinpin Street, Binondo China Town in 1988 as a seafood restaurant. Starting from humble beginnings has allowed North NorthPark restaurants have

been able to grow to maintain its honest-to-goodness ambiance, taste and service.

Chinoy comfort food that generations have come to know and love and that is North Park. Their food, their service and their values are what set them apart from the artifice of themed restaurants and the faddishness of trendy bars. Not only is North Park about a cool and modern ambiance, but it is also old-fashioned and well-loved cuisines.

As stated, the yellow trademark sign of North Park is our assurance of quality, value and consistent great taste. Its modern and yet no-nonsense ambiance and its many outlets across the metro make North Park the place for your entire family to get its fill, wherever they may be. Come as one or come as a dozen, North Park guarantees you a "sulit" experience. In present time, the North Park group of restaurants includes Next Door, Tiananmen Bar, Ma Chicken and Kopi Tiam. These restaurants have common dishes as well as unique menus. Each caters to specific sort of diner, whether they are large families, young urban professionals, trendy bar-hoppers, or coffee aficionados.

The purpose of this study is to help North Park Noodle House in their management style and also to find out what factors is needed to help the employees to be more satisfied. Lastly it will also help them to have more productive employees to help the company to continuously grow.

As North Park continues to grow, it continues to foster its homegrown feel and authentic comfort food menu making it the modern Chinoy restaurant we all love. The research study entitled "Manager's Management Style, Employees' Productivity and Satisfaction at North Park Noodle House" is relevant both to the industry, academe and the proponent for this can alleviate the knowledge on a particular type of business and location of the subject matter.

From these premises, the researcher attempted to determine the Manager's Management Style, Employee Satisfaction and Productivity at North Park Noodle House.

METHODS

This study examined the managers' management style and its relationship with employees' productivity and satisfaction at North Park Noodle House. A descriptive-correlational research design was employed, as it is an effective approach for determining existing relationships among variables. Data were gathered using a survey technique to obtain large-scale information about current conditions and to allow generalization. The respondents consisted of employees from two branches: twenty-nine (29) employees from the SLEX Shell branch (Day 1, 10:00 a.m. to 12:00 a.m.) and twenty-four (24) employees from the SLEX Caltex branch (Day 2, 9:00 a.m. to 12:00 a.m.), for a total of fifty-four (54) respondents. Although all available employees were enumerated, the researcher identified a minimum of 30 respondents as sufficient to strengthen the study, consistent

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with recommendations for descriptive research (Mann, 2010; Gay & Diehl, 1992, as cited in Hill, 2012). Random sampling was also applied to ensure representation.

To evaluate the variables, a four-point scale was used to assess managers' management style, employees' productivity, and satisfaction, with corresponding numerical ranges and verbal interpretations (Very High, High, Low, Very Low). For productivity and satisfaction, categorical responses (Strongly Agree to Strongly Disagree) were also included. The weighted mean was utilized to determine (a) managers' management style as perceived by employees, (b) employees' level of productivity, and (c) employees' level of

satisfaction. Meanwhile, the Pearson r correlation coefficient was used to test whether significant relationships exist between (a) management style and productivity, (b) management style and satisfaction, and (c) productivity and satisfaction.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Discussion of manager's management style, employees' satisfaction and employees' productivity of North Park Noodle House on Binan Laguna is shown the following table and textual presentation.

Table 1. Summary Table of Managers' Management Style as Assessed by the Employees

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Rank
1. Autocratic	3.25	High	4
2. Consultative	3.40	High	3
3. Democratic	3.55	Very High	2
4. Laissez-faire	3.65	Very High	1
Overall Weighted Mean	3.46	High	

Table 1 presents the summary table of managers' management style as assessed by the employees. Ranked 1 was "Laissez-faire" with a weighted mean 3.65 which is interpreted as "Very High", ranked 2 was "Democratic" with a weighted mean of 3.55 which is interpreted as "Very High",

ranked 3 was "Consultative" with a weighted mean of 3.40 which is interpreted as "High" and ranked 4 was "Autocratic" with a weighted mean of 3.25 which is interpreted as "High". As computed, it turns out that the average weighted mean for all of these is 3.46 which is interpreted as "High".

Table 2. Employees' Level of Satisfaction

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Rank
1. I am happy working with my colleagues	3.57	Very High	5.5
2. I am always positive when it comes to my working assignment	3.63	Very High	3
3. I always find ways to make my work easier and efficient	3.53	Very High	7
4. I encourage my co-worker to be motivated and to take initiative on their work/s.	3.43	High	8.5
5. I create a culture of mutual trust and respect to have a freer flow of communication and feedback throughout the organization	3.43	High	8.5
6. I encourage myself to have a personal accountability and taking ownership over task	3.57	Very High	5.5
7. I feel satisfied to the leadership of my managers	3.63	Very High	3
8. I feel part of a team working toward a shared goal	3.63	Very High	3
9. I feel physically safe in my work environment	3.37	High	10
10. My manager acknowledge when i do my work well.	3.73	Very High	1
Average Weighted Mean	3.55	Very High	

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Table 2 presents the employees’ level of satisfaction at North Park Noodle House. Ranked 1 was “My manager acknowledge when i do my work well” with a weighed mean of 3.73 which is interpreted as “Very High”, ranked 3 were “I am always positive when it comes to my working assignment”, “I feel satisfied to the leadership of my managers”, and “I feel part of a team working toward a shared goal” with the same weighted mean of 3.63 which is interpreted as “Very High”, ranked 5.5 were “I am happy working with my colleagues” and “I encourage myself to have a personal accountability and taking ownership over task” with the same weighted mean of 3.57 which is interpreted as “Very High”, ranked 7 was “I always find ways to make my work easier and efficient” with a weighted mean of 3.53 which is interpreted as “Very High”, ranked 8.5 were “ I encourage my co-worker to be motivated and to take initiative on their work/s” and “I create a culture of mutual trust and respect to have a freer flow of communication and

feedback throughout the organization” with the same weighted mean of 3.43 which is interpreted as “High” and ranked 10 was “I feel physically safe in my work environment” with weighted mean of 3.43 which is interpreted as “High”. As computed, it turns out that the average weighted mean for all of these is 3.55 which is interpreted as “Very High”.

The findings of the study support the claims of Regine (2017), stated that employee satisfaction is of the utmost importance for staff to remain happy and to achieve their best level as well. Satisfied workers are the ones who, even in the worst scenario, are extremely loyal to their organization and stick to it. They do not act out of any compulsion, but because they want to take their business to a new stage. Employees need to be passionate about their job, and only when employees are satisfied with their job and organization as a whole does the passion come.

Table 3. Employees’ Level of Productivity

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Rank
1. I am always going to work on time	3.40	High	8
2. I am able to finish my duties and responsibilities efficiently	3.47	High	7
3. I know how my job impact the mission of the company	3.53	Very High	5
4. I am able to use properly all the equipment	3.60	Very High	2.5
5. I will always offer help to my colleague	3.60	Very High	2.5
6. I feel encourage to come up with new and better ways of doing things	3.60	Very High	2.5
7. I follow all the standard operating procedure	3.37	High	9.5
8. I will able to handle guest complaint	3.37	High	9.5
9. I will able to multitask on my station	3.60	Very High	2.5
10. I can give solutions to every problem that may I encounter	3.50	High	6
Average Weighted Mean	3.50	High	

Table 3 presents the employees’ level of productivity at North Park Noodle House. Ranked 2.5 were “I am able to use properly all the equipment”, “I will always offer help to my colleague”, “I feel encourage to come up with new and better ways of doing things”, and “I will able to multitask on my station” with the same weighted mean of 3.60 which is interpreted as “Very High”, ranked 5 was “I know how my job impact the mission of the company” with weighted mean of 3.43 which is interpreted as “Very High”, ranked 6 was “I can give solutions to every problem that may I encounter” with weighted mean of 3.50 which is interpreted as “High”,

ranked 7 was “ I am able to finish my duties and responsibilities efficiently” with weighted mean of 3.47 which is interpreted as “High”, ranked 8 was “I am always going to work on time” with weighted mean of 3.40 which is interpreted as “High” and ranked 9.5 were “I follow all the standard operating procedure” and “I will able to handle guest complaint” with the same weighted mean of 3.37 which is interpreted as “High”. As computed, it turns out that the average weighted mean for all of these is 3.50 which is interpreted as “High”.

The findings of the study support the claims of Hanaysha (2016), stated that productivity in the workplace is an important aspect of any company and progress is just around the corner when this notion is grasped by top management. Nevertheless, if your employer does not give you the chance to increase productivity, because the lifeblood of your company is running out, you may want to start

looking for another job. Moreover, an appropriate management style paves the way for ambitious strategies to achieve long-term organizational objectives. It also allows us to conclude which style of management is the most critical in telecommuting workers and managers for the highest level of productivity.

Table 4. Relationship Between the Managers’ Management Style and Employees’ Level of Satisfaction

Managers’ Management Style	Pearson r	p value	Interpretation
Autocratic	-0.239	0.204	Not Significant
Consultative	-0.018	0.925	Not Significant
Democratic	0.458	0.011	*Significant
Laissez-faire	0.635	0.000	**Significant

*0.05 level of significance

**0.01 level of significance

As shown in the table, for the relationship between the managers’ management style in terms of autocratic and consultative and employees’ level of satisfaction, Pearson r values of -0.239 and -0.018, respectively, were obtained. p values of 0.204 and 0.925, respectively, were obtained which were higher than the 0.05 level of significance showed that there is no significant relationship between the managers’ management style as to autocratic and consultative and employees’ level of satisfaction. The employees’ level of satisfaction is not dependent on the managers’ management style in terms of autocratic and consultative.

The finding of the study for the relationship of management style in terms of autocratic support the claims of Cherry (2020), stated that autocratic leadership can be beneficial at times, there are also many instances where this leadership style can be problematic. People who abuse an autocratic leadership style are often viewed as bossy, controlling, and dictatorial. This can sometimes result in resentment among group members. Meanwhile, the finding of the study for the relationship of management style in terms of consultative support the claims of Villamor (2020), states that this is also a top-down structure where the ultimate decision-making authority is open to management. It is less successful than other types and can slow down the process of decision-making and hinder the implementation of significant

changes. Experts claim it is necessary to sparingly use this style so that you do not damage your company's development.

For the relationship between the managers’ management style in terms of democratic and laissez-faire and employees’ level of satisfaction, Pearson r values of 0.458 and 0.635, respectively, were obtained. p values of 0.011 and 0.000, respectively, were obtained which were lower than the 0.05 and 0.01 level of significance respectively, showed that there is significant relationship between the managers’ management style as to democratic and laissez-faire and employees’ level of satisfaction. The more the managers practice democratic and laissez-faire style of management, the higher is the employees’ level of satisfaction.

The findings of the study support the claims of Webster (2018), stated that democratic leadership, one of the most productive management types, promotes organizational teamwork and offers staff an active role in the decision-making process. This form of style of leadership can have a number of effects on workers. Meanwhile, for the relationship between management style in terms of laissez-faire and employees satisfaction support the claims of Kumar (2020), stated that empowering workers and improving productivity overall are the advantages of the laissez-faire leadership model. This sort of leadership can also help a team become more imaginative and boost morale as a whole.

Table 5. Relationship Between the Managers’ Management Style and Employees’ Level of Productivity

Managers’ Management Style	Pearson r	p value	Interpretation
Autocratic	-0.210	0.266	Not Significant
Consultative	-0.140	0.462	Not Significant
Democratic	0.221	0.240	Not Significant
Laissez-faire	0.479	0.007	*Significant

0.05 level of significance

*0.01 level of significance

As shown in the table, for the relationship between the managers’ management style in terms of autocratic, consultative and democratic and employees’ level of productivity, Pearson r values of -0.210, -0.140 and 0.221, respectively, were obtained. P values of 0.266, 0.462 and 0.240, respectively, were obtained which were higher than the 0.05 level of significance showed that there is no significant relationship between the managers’ management style as to autocratic, consultative and democratic and employees’ level of productivity. The employees’ level of productivity is not dependent on the managers’ management style in terms of autocratic, consultative and democratic. For the relationship between the managers’ management style in terms of laissez-faire and employees’ level of productivity A Pearson r value of 0.479 was obtained. A p value of 0.007 was obtained which was lower than the 0.01 level of significance showed that

there is significant relationship between the managers’ management style as to laissez-faire and employees’ level of productivity. The more the managers practice laissez-faire style of management, the higher is the employees’ level of productivity.

The finding of the study support the claims of Heibutzki (2020), stated that the most significant measure of progress or failure at work is an employee's relationship with a boss. Via behavior modeling, positive feedback, and performance evaluations, among other approaches, managers have various ways to influence employee performance. These strategies, however, won't work unless the boss attempts to consider the motives of his staff. Managers who follow a leadership model of "command and control" encourage lower loyalty and efficiency than those who allow any degree of autonomy for their subordinates.

Table 6. Relationship Between the Employees’ Level of Satisfaction and Level of Productivity

Variables	Pearson r	p value	Interpretation
Employees’ Level of Satisfaction and Level of Productivity	0.558	0.001	Significant

As shown in the table, for the relationship between the employees’ level of satisfaction and level of productivity, a Pearson r value of 0.558 was obtained. A p value of 0.001 which was lower than the 0.01 level of significance showed that there is significant relationship between the employees’ level of satisfaction and level of productivity. The higher is the employees’ level of satisfaction, the higher is their level of productivity.

The findings of the study support that claims of an article posted by PBC, stated that a research at the University of Warwick by economists showed that happy workers were 12 percent more productive, while unhappy employees were 10 percent less productive. It will impact their efficiency if workers feel bored and undervalued.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The study revealed that the managers of North Park Noodle House exhibit high levels of autocratic and consultative management styles, while democratic and laissez-faire styles are practiced at a very high level. Employees demonstrated a very high level of satisfaction and a high level of productivity. Findings further showed that employees’ satisfaction is not influenced by autocratic and consultative styles but increases when democratic and laissez-faire approaches are applied. Similarly, employee productivity is not dependent on autocratic, consultative, and democratic styles, but it improves with the use of laissez-faire management. Moreover, a strong positive relationship exists between employees’ satisfaction and productivity, indicating that higher satisfaction leads to higher productivity.

Based on these findings, it is recommended that North Park Noodle House continue and strengthen the use of democratic and laissez-faire management styles to sustain and enhance both employee satisfaction and productivity. Management may use this study as a basis for understanding the significant relationships between leadership styles, employee satisfaction, and productivity, allowing them to refine their managerial approaches accordingly. Additionally, future researchers are encouraged to replicate or extend this study by exploring other variables and contemporary management styles that may further influence employee outcomes in modern organizational settings.

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